

GROWTH PERFORMANCE, AMINO ACID AND FATTY ACID COMPOSITION OF GILTHEAD SEABREAM (*Sparus aurata*) FED ALGAE MEAL DIETS

A. Tampou^{1*}, K. Kousoulaki², A. Vasilaki³, I. Nengas³, I. T. Karapanagiotidis¹, E. Mente⁴

¹School of Agricultural Science, Department of Ichthyology and Aquatic Environment, University of Thessaly, Fytoko Street, GR-38446, Volos, Greece

²Nofima AS, Feed Technology Centre, Kjerreidviken 16, N-5141 Fyllingsdalen, Norway

³Institute of Marine Biology, Biotechnology & Aquaculture, Hellenic Center for Marine Research, Anavyssos, 19013, Athens, Greece

⁴ School of Veterinary Medicine, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, Greece

Email: tampou@uth.gr

Introduction

Aquaculture sector is thriving as a response to the rapidly increased demand for seafood products. The sector is using 18 million tons of wild fish that are targeted for fishmeals and fish oils in aquafeeds (FAO 2020), thus affecting the sustainability of marine ecosystem. This has led the research to focus on environmentally sustainable sources of proteins and lipids as replacements of fishmeal and fish oil. Microalgae biomasses seem to be potential feed ingredients containing sustainable amounts of essential amino acids, essential fatty acids, vitamins, and pigments, that could be produced with a low environmental footprint (Nagappan et al. 2021). This study aims to investigate the effect of dietary inclusion of algae meal on the growth performance, amino acid composition and fatty acid composition of the white muscle of gilthead sea bream (*Sparus aurata*).

Material and methods

The experimental trial was conducted at the Department of Ichthyology and Aquatic Environment, University of Thessaly, in Volos, Greece. Briefly, 360 individuals *S. aurata* (initial mean weight 6.43±0.04g) were distributed randomly to six 250l tanks. Two experimental diets were formulated to be isonitrogenous, isolipidic, and isoenergetic with diet 1 (PA) consisted of 8% *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, and diet 2 (HA) consisted of 8.23% *Schizochytrium limacinum*. Each diet was assigned to triplicate groups of 60 fish per group. The trial lasted 45 days, after 15 days of acclimatization. The fish were fed three times per day *ad libitum*. Fish were weighted individually at the beginning and end of the experimental trial under anaesthesia. Feed consumption was recorded daily in order to evaluate accurately values for feed utilization.

Results

The results showed that weight gain, feed consumption, specific growth rate and survival did not have statistically significant differences ($p>0.05$) between fish fed the diet consisted of *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* (PA) and the diet of *Schizochytrium limacinum* (HA). Fish fed with PA had statistically significant ($p<0.05$) lower feed conversion ratio and higher protein efficiency ratio (Table 1).

Amino acid composition revealed a strong positive correlation, highly significant ($p<0.05$) between diets and the white muscle of fish in each treatment. Moreover, fatty acids analysis showed a significant decrease ($p<0.05$) of eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) and an increase ($p<0.05$) of docosahexaenoic acid (DHA) in white muscle of seabream fed the HA diet, compared to the PA treatment. Arachidonic acid (ARA) of white muscle was unaffected ($p>0.05$) between the dietary treatments.

Table 1: Growth performance parameters of gilthead seabream fed the experimental diets.

	PA	HA
Final Weight (g)	26.54±0.34 ^a	26.62±0.35 ^a
Weight gain (g)	20.07±0.34 ^a	20.22±0.35 ^a
Feed consumption (g/fish)	15.48±0.53 ^a	17.89±0.78 ^a
Specific growth rate (SGR, %/day)	3.10±0.02 ^a	3.13±0.02 ^a
Feed conversion ratio (FCR)	0.81±0.01 ^a	0.93±0.01 ^b
Protein efficiency ratio (PER)	2.92±0.04 ^b	2.52±0.04 ^a
Survival (%)	98.88±0.55 ^a	99.44±0.55 ^a

Values are presented as means±standard error. Means sharing the same superscript are not significantly different from each other ($P<0.05$).

(Continued on next page)

Discussion

The results of this study showed that the inclusion of algae meal in *S. aurata* diets did not affect growth performance and amino acid deposition. The lower FCR and higher PER exhibited in fish fed the PA diet denotes a better protein utilization of *P. tricornutum* diet than *S. limacinum* by *S. aurata*. In terms of aquaculture sustainability, the substitution of fish oil with heterotrophically produced microalgae in salmon feeds proved the nutritional feasibility of low trophic level organisms such as algae in aquaculture fish feed (Kousoulaki et al., 2017). In accordance with the results of this work, fishmeal replacement with the microalgae *P. tricornutum* in started diets of *S. aurata* showed that SGR was not affected ($p>0.05$) and there was an increase of saturated fatty acids in fish (Atalah et al. 2007). Moreover, the inclusion of 2.5% *P. tricornutum* in finishing diets of gilthead sea bream did not significantly change growth, feed utilization parameters and muscle fatty acid profile ($p>0.05$) (Ribeiro et al. 2017). Furthermore, the 2.5% inclusion of *Schizochytrium* sp. as lipid source and especially DHA source in microdiets of *S. aurata* had no negative effect on larvae (Ganuza et al. 2008). In contrast to the forementioned authors, Eryalçin & Yildiz (2015) reported that the replacement of fishoil with dried *Schizochytrium* sp. meal had a negative effect on growth of seabream although the DHA was increased.

The differences found in the fatty acid profiles on the muscle tissue of fish are characteristic to the fatty acid's profiles of each algae species as *S. limacinum* is known for being richer in DHA and poorer in EPA compared to the *P. tricornutum* and *S. limacinum* has been used successfully in the diets of seabream and other species, mainly for fishoil replacement. According to Santigosa et al. (2021), the growth performance of seabream fed 3.5% *Schizochytrium* sp. oil as replacement of fishoil was unaffected and fillet fatty acid composition was in accordance with the diet fatty acid composition, suggesting that dietary microalgae could lead to an environmentally friendly final product rich in n-3, n-6 fatty acids. The dietary inclusion of algae meal (*Phaeodactylum tricornutum* and *Schizochytrium limacinum*) does not influence growth performance but there is an effect on FCR, PER, amino acid deposition and fatty acid composition of the white muscle of seabream (*Sparus aurata*) follows the fatty acid and amino acid composition of the two algae suggesting they can be used and produce a final product rich in n-3 and n-6 fatty acids. Algae meal biomass is promising ingredient to move the formulation of sea bream feed to a more sustainable future.

Acknowledgement

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Innovation Action, FutureEUAqua, under grant agreement No 817737. This output reflects the views only of the author(s), and the European Union cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

References

- Atalah, E., Cruz, C. M. H., Izquierdo, M. S., Rosenlund, G., Caballero, M. J., Valencia, A., & Robaina, L. (2007). Two microalgae *Cryptocodinium cohnii* and *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* as alternative source of essential fatty acids in starter feeds for seabream (*Sparus aurata*). *Aquaculture*, 270(1–4), 178–185.
- Eryalçin, K. M., & Yildiz, M. (2015). Effects of long-term feeding with dried microalgae added microdiets on growth and fatty acid composition on gilthead sea bream (*Sparus aurata* L., 1758). *Turkish Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences*, 15, 899–909.
- FAO (2020). The state of world fisheries and aquaculture 2020. Sustainability in action. Rome.
- Ganuza, E., Benítez-Santana, T., Atalah, E., Vega-Orellana, O., Ganga, R., & Izquierdo, M. S. (2008). *Cryptocodinium cohnii* and *Schizochytrium* sp. as potential substitutes to fisheries-derived oils from seabream (*Sparus aurata*) microdiets. *Aquaculture*, 277(1–2), 109–116.
- Kousoulaki, K., Carlehög, M., Mørkøre, T., Ytrestøyl, T., Ruyter, B., Berge, G.M. (2017): Long term supplementation of Heterotrophic microalgae in Atlantic salmon diets. Aquaculture Europe 2017, Dubrovnic, Croatia, 17-20 October, 2017.
- Nagappan, S., Das, P., Quadir, M. A., Thaher, M., Khan, S., Mahata, C., Al-Jabri, H., Vatland, A. K., & Kumar, G., (2021). Potential of microalgae as a sustainable feed ingredient for aquaculture. *Journal of Biotechnology*, 341 (1-20).
- Ribeiro, A. R., Gonçalves, A., Barbeiro, M., Bandarra, N., Nunes, M. L., Carvalho, M. L., Silva, J., Navalho, J., Dinis, M. T., Silva, T., & Dias, J. (2017). *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* in finishing diets for gilthead seabream: effects on skin pigmentation, sensory properties and nutritional value. *Journal of Applied Phycology*, 29(4), 1945–1956.
- Santigosa, E., Brambilla, F., & Milanese, L. (2021). Microalgae oil as an effective alternative source of EPA and DHA for gilthead seabream (*Sparus aurata*) aquaculture. *Animals*, 11(971).